

Multi-component Application Mapping across the Continuum

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Abstract. This paper presents a novel orchestrating mechanism for multi-component applications across the continuum. The orchestration mechanism provides an initial components-to-nodes mapping at launch time and, in case of anomaly detection at runtime, reschedules the application layout to meet the performance objectives within the application-specified constraints. The mapping engine, named Match Maker, is a core component inside the ICOS research project, an intelligent metaOS conceived to leverage the capabilities of the continuum. It is fed with abundant and accurate information collected at runtime from the telemetry component and enriched with additional information from the forecasting system generated by the intelligence layer. The novelty of the orchestrating mechanism is that the provided layout distributes the application components across the continuum, fulfilling the application requirements and constraints in the selected nodes, and considering the interdependence effects between selected nodes. In addition, the application can define policies for layout decisions based on performance and security, and policies for anomaly detection and remediation actions.

1 Introduction

The continuum has been defined as an extension of the traditional cloud towards multiple entities, such as edge, fog, and the IoT, providing analysis, processing, storage, and data generation capabilities [1]. The continuum not only leverages the individual advantages of the different computing paradigms, this is, unlimited computing and storage capabilities in the cloud and low latency and privacy preservation at the edge, but also provides added value from the combination of cloud and edge computing technologies, such as reduced network traffic and energy consumption, faster response times, and improved data security.

Seamless continuum management poses several critical challenges that must be addressed. For instance, managing a large number of highly heterogeneous resources (ranging from constrained devices to complex clusters of powerful computers), considering resources' dynamicity and volatility, facilitating data access while guaranteeing data privacy and ensuring security, or facilitating interoperability among the different nodes' virtualization technologies. The primary goal of a continuum management environment is to provide an effective and efficient

orchestration of data and computation. Orchestration includes mapping the application components to the available computing infrastructure that fulfills the application requirements, as well as dynamically adapting the execution workflows to meet performance objectives within cost and budget constraints. An effective orchestration must consider the application requirements, the capabilities of the nodes and their current state, the data sources location, accessibility and privacy constraints, the network characteristics and its current state, and the runtime interrelation between the different components of the application.

Container orchestration and resources management at cluster level is a relatively mature topic with several well-known products on the market, such as Kubernetes [2] or Docker Swarm [3]. However, extending the scope of management and orchestration to multi-cluster, heterogeneous edge environments, or the combination of both, i.e., the continuum, becomes a more challenging topic of current research, which is attracting attention of a large number of researchers, academics, and tech developers.

In this paper, a comprehensive orchestration mechanism for multi-component applications across the continuum is presented. The orchestration mechanism provides an initial mapping for the multi-component application and, in case of anomaly detection during runtime, reschedules the application layout to mitigate performance loss. The multi-component application is mapped across heterogeneous nodes in the continuum according to the requirements and constraints defined in the application, and the application layout is optimized to meet the performance metrics and security standards defined by the user. Additionally, user-defined policies are used to detect execution anomalies at runtime and remap application components accordingly to recover from policy violations.

The mapping engine, internally named Match Maker (MM), is part of the ICOS research project, an intelligent metaOS conceived to leverage the capabilities of the continuum [4]. The MM engine has been designed to provide the following advantages:

- An optimized mapping for multi-component applications across the continuum according to the requirements and constraints defined as part of the application description.
- Dynamic rescheduling decisions for multi-component remapping to react at minimal cost upon policy violations.
- Considering the interdependence effects of multi-component application distributed along the continuum.
- Considering the current availability of nodes for mapping decisions, as well as an estimation of the predicted availability for ahead-of-time decisions.
- Considering user-defined policies for layout decisions based on performance, security, or even a combination of them.
- Considering user-defined policies for monitoring runtime performance features, anomaly detection, and execution of remediation actions.

The remainder of this paper has been organized as follows. Section 2 reviews some related work from the literature. In Section 3 the Match Maker module

is described. Section 4 illustrates some qualitative evaluation of the proposed method. And finally, Section 5 concludes this work.

2 Related Works

Various orchestration tools like Kubernetes [2] and Docker Swarm [3] are commercially available for the management of a large number of containerized applications. A comparative analysis of these tools is described in [5]. However, each of these tools has its own limitations. Kubernetes is best in scheduling but cannot satisfy heterogeneous IoT applications with diverse networks in edge computing. Docker Swarm is easy to use but does not support automatic application scaling and load balancing.

Most research works based their contributions on extending these orchestration tools. The study in [6] proposes optimal mapping of latency-sensitive workload in the kubernetes edge cluster by extending the default kubernetes scheduler. The telemetry data collected is restricted to network metrics and it does not support multi-cluster scenarios. In [7] the authors extend kubernetes with network-aware and self-adaptive placement capabilities. A greedy heuristic approach is used for the optimal placement. The problem with the solution is that applications considered are single-component. In [8], a fog computing platform is presented where the mapping of components to devices is based on the kubernetes labelling mechanism. However, the scheduler is unable to efficiently allocate pods because the resources information is not accurate. In [9], a dynamic scheduling strategy is presented that monitors changes in the infrastructure and application states. However, they did not consider any user defined policy and detailed telemetry data. The authors in [10] implement a scalable and extensible framework in federated fog environments. A heuristic approach is applied to solve the mapping problem. However, the limitation is the lack of a security mechanism for data transmission across clusters and time-series data. In [11], the authors present a new docker swarm strategy integrated into the docker swarm scheduler. However, it takes into account only the CPU utilisation.

Compared to the previous work, this paper deploys a multi-component application across the continuum without any constraints in the local cluster network, taking into consideration the computational resources of the nodes (CPU cores, RAM, architecture type, and any peripherals attached). Moreover, a high-security policy is implemented while making placement decisions for the components. To the best of our knowledge, no one has implemented user defined security policy while considering multi-component placement in heterogeneous environment. We also allow users to define more advanced policies and the specification of remediation actions if there is any violation to those policies.

3 The Match Maker

The Match Maker (MM) is the responsible to decide the application-components mapping across the continuum, as part of the ICOS project. ICOS is a EU funded

research project aimed to design, develop and validate a meta operating system for a continuum [4]. ICOS has been conceived as a three-layer system, with the Meta-Kernel Layer in its core, the Intelligence Layer and Security Layer that feed and protect the kernel, and a transversal Data Management plane. A more detailed view of the ICOS architecture can be found at [12].

The Meta-Kernel Layer provides the base functionalities necessary to make resources in the continuum manageable and to orchestrate data and applications efficiently. Two main blocks implement the kernel: the continuum manager and the runtime manager. The continuum manager keeps track of the available resources in the continuum as well as their current state. The runtime manager is the responsible for ensuring the ICOS nodes to fulfil execution requests efficiently. The MM is in the core of the runtime manager, and is the responsible to provide the application-components mapping over the nodes in ICOS.

3.1 The MM Interface

The MM uses two data structures as input: the manifest file that describes the application and user preferences, and the ICOS topology. It generates as output a list of <component-node> mapping tuples.

The manifest file identifies the list of components of the application, and includes, for each component, its requirements and constraints. Additionally, it contains some ICOS-specific policies that specify which metrics should be considered during the optimization process, what threshold has to be met during execution, or what actions should be taken when anomalies are detected. For example, one application component could specify to run on an ARM architecture (constraint) with 2 cores, 4GB of available RAM, and needing access to a certain IoT device (requirements), and to prefer a node that minimizes throughput while guaranteeing security (weighting performance and security with 60% and 40%, respectively) and, in case that throughput is below X iterations per second, then scaling-up dynamically the deployment (policies).

The ICOS topology describes the set of available nodes in the ICOS continuum along with information about their IoT peripherals and attached data sources, and includes their current availability (obtained through the runtime telemetry) as well as their predicted usage (obtained through the Intelligence Layer¹). Nodes are labeled with a security score (SCA, obtained dynamically through the Security Layer), and the topology also includes information about the nodes interconnectivity, representing latency and throughput.

3.2 The MM Algorithm

The MM algorithm is based on a scoring mechanism and considers the application requirements, as well as the inter-nodes affinity, to select the best set of nodes to run a multi-component application. An overview of the algorithm, shown in Algorithm 1, is as follows:

¹ Although the predicted information provisioning in ICOS is currently under development, the MM engine is ready to use this information.

Algorithm 1 Pseudo-code of the MM algorithm

```

components ← parseComponents(appmanifest)
topology ← getICOSTopology()
for c ∈ components do
    candidates[i] ← filterNodes(topology, c → requirements)
    scoreNodes(candidates[i], c → policies)
end for
for c ∈ components do
    addAffinity(candidates, topology)
end for
mapping ← selectBest(candidates)

```

After parsing the application manifest and retrieving the ICOS topology, the first step is, for each component, processing a filtering stage: candidate nodes are selected per component if they meet all component’s requirements and constraints. Currently, components can request a specific processor architecture (intel or ARM), some CPU features, free RAM capacity, and specific data sources, volumes, or IoT devices. Note that updated information on the current status of nodes as well as the predicted information on their availability in the near future are obtained from the ICOS continuum manager. Candidate nodes are then scored according to the component policies. In the current MM version, policies can specify whether nodes must be selected based on performance features, security features, or a combination of both (in this case, the manifest can specify the weight % to be considered for each criteria).

After the first loop, a weighted list of candidate nodes that meet the application requirements has been generated for each component of the application. Then, a second loop adds affinity weights between all nodes of different components (all-to-all assessment). These weights represent the interrelation cost between nodes of different components (latency and throughput), and are obtained from the topology information. The affinity facilitates the selection of close nodes based on locality. In this stage, a highly connected graph with per node scoring and inter-node affinity weights is obtained.

The final stage is the selection of the best candidates per component. This has been implemented through a maximum-flow algorithm that selects the best combination of nodes that provide the maximal scoring while minimizing the inter-node affinity costs. The maximum-flow algorithm has been extended to consider saturation so that a single node can be selected by more than one component as long as the accumulated constraints required by the components are met by this node. The output of the MM algorithm is a list of <component-node> mapping tuples that optimize the required metrics (performance and security) while meeting the application requirements and constraints.

3.3 Components Remapping

Once the application has been deployed through the selected nodes, one ICOS component from the runtime manager block in the Distributed Meta-Kernel Layer, named the Policy Manager, monitors the telemetry generated at runtime to detect an eventual execution anomaly, as defined in the policy information from the application manifest. In case of anomaly detection, the Policy Manager launches an event along with the proposed recovery actions.

In case that the remediation actions involve a remapping of the application components (either scaling up, scaling down, or just remapping), then the MM module will be invoked again for a remapping. Scaling up means adding more nodes (for instance, adding replicas to a specific component), scaling down means removing some nodes (removing replicas), and remapping means changing the execution layout, either because some nodes are underperforming, or because some new nodes with clear better performance join the ICOS topology.

In either case, the MM algorithm will be invoked as previously described, but with some additional constraints to favor the current running nodes and penalize the cost of component migration. For instance, in the case of remapping, again the candidate nodes will be generated per component and, in this case, the new nodes will be added to the previous list of candidates. The new nodes will presumably have a higher scoring (if they have clear better performance); however, an extra cost will be added to all candidate nodes (except the nodes that are currently running the component) to reflect the overhead of task migration. This means that application remapping will only be proposed when the cost of migration is absorbed by the benefits of running on a new (more powerful) node.

4 Evaluation

This section illustrates the behavior of the MM algorithm through a set of small experiments. For the sake of simplicity a reduced fixed topology depicted in Fig. 1 is considered. In this example, for simplicity, each node is described by a performance scoring, a security scoring, and the amount available memory.

4.1 Basic mapping without restrictions

We consider a simple application with two components $C1$ and $C2$. None of them has any specified requirement and the policy is set to performance. After the filtering phase, all nodes are candidate nodes for both components as they do not have requirements. A graph is created as shown in Fig. 2. The algorithm sets the performance scoring of each node (shown in the figure) plus inter-node affinity (represented as negative weight at the edges). The algorithm then finds the path that goes through one node in each layer (component) with the maximum result. For this example it results in the mapping of all components to $N1$ as this is the best option (the most powerful node) and all components can be deployed on it.

Fig. 1. Considered topology showing two relatively more powerful nodes at the cloud and two nodes at the edge with their corresponding scoring and attached resources

Fig. 2. Mapping result for a basic experiment without requirements.

4.2 Memory requirement

In this experiment a requirement of memory has been added to *C2*. In the topology only *N2* satisfies the memory requirement therefore *C2* is mapped to *N2*. In Fig. 3 we can see the candidate nodes for each component after the filtering phase, which shows that only *N2* is a candidate for *C2*. The weights are set as in the previous example according to the policy selected, and the resulting mapping for *C1* is *N1* which has the highest result (the computation for each combination is shown in cursive at the top of the figure).

This example also shows that each time a component is selected, the weights are adjusted to reflect the placement. In this case the algorithm has taken into account that *N2* is fully occupied with *C2* (as all the memory is booked) so *N2* is not considered as a candidate for *C1*.

4.3 Node affinity

In this example *C1* requires a camera and only the *N4* edge node complies with this device requirement. The filtering result, shown in Fig. 4, reflects that *N4* is

Fig. 3. Mapping result for an experiment with memory requirements.

the only candidate for $C1$. The scores are set taking into account performance. Despite $N1$ (the most powerful node) is a candidate for $C2$, once the node affinity weights are considered, the mapping of $C2$ results in $N2$.

Fig. 4. Mapping result for an experiment with a camera requirement, showing how node affinity affects the mapping decision.

4.4 Security

Security requirements can be considered in two ways: (i) as a hard requirement (i.e. a particular component needs to run in a highly secure node); or (ii) as a soft requirement or policy (i.e. maximize the security of the application). Let us see an experiment of both scenarios.

When security is set as a requirement, the mapping algorithm considers it at the filtering phase. In other words, a node will not be a candidate if its security score does not reach a certain threshold. For our experiment we set this threshold to 60. Taking the previous example, we add security to $C2$. Fig. 5 shows the

result of the algorithm. After the filtering phase *N1* is not a candidate as it did not meet the security requirement. Among the remaining candidate nodes, the performance scores are taken into account to select the best fit, resulting in *N2*.

Fig. 5. Mapping result for an experiment with security as a requirement.

Security can also be set as a policy, in this case the security scores are taken into account when selecting the best candidate. Moreover, policy can combine several metrics. In this example the policy is set to 50% performance and 50% security. Fig. 6 shows the result of the algorithm, and the table below the graph shows the score computations for each path. With this policy, *N3* is selected as the best fit for *C2*.

Fig. 6. Mapping result with an experiment where security is set as policy.

5 Conclusions

This paper presents a sophisticated orchestration tool for multi-component applications across the continuum, as part of the ICOS research project. The novelty of the mechanism lies in the fact that the provided mapping can be placed at any node of the continuum as long as the application requirements are met and the objective cost metrics are minimized. The application description model specifies the requirements and constraints per component, but also some ICOS specific policies for layout decisions based on performance and security, and for anomalies detection and remediation management. The orchestration engine provides a mapping at launch time for each application component, and a remapping strategy at runtime in case of anomaly detection. The evaluation section provides some illustrative examples of the mapping mechanism and its capability.

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